

LIVER IMMUNITY AND ITS IMPORTANCE FOR HUMAN HEALTH

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Annotation. This article discusses the liver, one of the internal organs of living organisms. Liver is one of the most important organs in our body. There are separate places about the formation of liver immunity and paying special attention to it.

Key words: liver, hepatocytes, segment, filter, metabolism, hepatitis, fibrosis, cirrhosis, liver cancer.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается печень, один из внутренних органов живых организмов. Печень является одним из самых важных органов в нашем организме. Отдельные места посвящены формированию печеночного иммунитета и уделению ему особого внимания.

Ключевые слова: печень, гепатоциты, сегмент, фильтр, метаболизм, гепатит, фиброз, цирроз, рак печени.

The liver is the largest parenchymatous organ in the human body, it is composed of 300 billion liver cells (hepatocytes), these cells contain 2000 types of enzymes, they mediate all biochemical reactions in the body and participate in vital processes in the body. Therefore, the liver is called "it is called a complex chemical factory of the organism". The liver plays a major role in detoxifying the body, managing metabolism, producing and excreting bile, controlling blood clotting, and maintaining immunity.

Liver participates in sugar, protein and fat metabolism. Production and separation of grass. Hepatocytes produce and secrete bile, which then passes through the bile duct to the place where it is concentrated, the gallbladder. Every day, the liver produces 800 - 1000 mg of bile. The herb helps in the digestion of fats in the small intestine. Detoxification effect. Toxins and decomposition products formed in the metabolic process in the human body are separated and neutralized by the liver. These processes occur through oxidation, reduction, or combination with inorganic molecules. These substances are excreted through the kidneys after detoxification.

Liver disease causes many systems in the body to malfunction. For example, when the liver is damaged, the production of bile necessary for normal digestion is disrupted. This leads to loss of appetite, nausea, vomiting, etc. If liver cells are damaged, serum aminotrasferase increases and cholinolipase decreases, which leads to weakness, rapid fatigue, and drowsiness. Jaundice is observed when bile pigment metabolism is disturbed, lipid content in blood changes when sugar metabolism is disturbed. **N.H.Shomirzayev, S.Kh.Nazarov, R.J.Usmanov. "Topographic anatomy", Tashkent. "Academy", 2005. 166.**

The liver is the largest parenchymatous organ in the body and consists of 300 billion liver cells. There are 2,000 types of enzymes in these cells, which mediate all biochemical reactions in the body and take part in vital processes in the body. That is why the liver is called "a complex chemical factory of the body". Currently, with

the successful development of liver surgery, the understanding of the segmental structure of the liver is widespread. A segment is a region of the liver that has its own blood circulation, innervation, bile and lymphatic channels. It helps to surgically remove such areas of the liver without damaging the adjacent segments.

F. N. Bahadirov. "Human Anatomy", Tashkent. "Sharq", 2005. 33.

Segment is not only a spatial concept, it also reflects the branching characteristics of the gate system. A large branch of the portal vein enters the segment together with a branch of the hepatic artery, and the bile duct and lymphatic vessels leave the segment. Since the branching of the portal vein is not constant, researchers give different numbers of liver segments. Currently, there are several schemes of segmentation of the liver corresponding to the areas of blood supply, bile and lymph flow. But the most common is Kuino's scheme, according to which the liver is divided into 8 segments, which are different from each other. The liver lies in the abdominal cavity, under the diaphragm, under the right ribs. The liver develops from the endodermal epithelium of the initial part of the midgut (epithelium). In the third week of fetal life, the liver bud appears in the form of a ridge on the ventral wall of the midgut, and it is called a liver bud. This relief is first common, then it is divided into two upper and lower reliefs. If the liver tube and liver gland tissue appear from the upper bulge, the gallbladder develops from the lower bulge. The liver metabolizes hemoglobin in the blood, chemicals, drugs, alcohol and other preparations. The liver stores nutrients in the blood for use when needed. **Vengerovsky A.I. Pharmacological approaches to regulation of liver functions, Tashkent. "Barkamol Avlod", 2002. 73.**

Stores glucose, iron, copper, vitamins and B 9 (in red blood cell synthesis) B 12 vitamins. The liver synthesizes plasma proteins, and also produces liver hormones, fatty acids, bilirubin, and proteins. When necessary, hormones are synthesized and released from the liver. The hormones it produces include insulin-like growth factor, which promotes early growth and development.

In conclusion, we can say that the liver is one of the most important organs of our body. It is in our hands to protect it and ensure its safety.

LIST OF REFERENCES:

1. F. N. Bahadirov. "Human Anatomy", Tashkent. "Sharq", 2005. 33.
2. Vengerovsky A.I. Pharmacological approaches to regulation of liver functions, Tashkent. "Barkamol Avlod", 2002. 73.
3. F. N. Bahadirov. "Human Anatomy", Tashkent. "Sharq", 2005. 33.
4. Javodbek Mirzaali o'g'li, A. (2022). VITAMINLAR. VITAMIN HAQIDA TUSHUNCHA. VITAMINLARNING HOZIRGI KUNDA INSON HAYOTIDAGI AHAMIYATI. INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION, 1(11), 13–16. Retrieved from <http://interonconf.org/index.php/idre/article/view/264>
5. Asfandiyorov Javodbek Mirzaali o'g'li, Mardonov Mirzabek Begzod o'g'li, Sultonmirzayev Xikmatillo Eminjon o'g'li, Saydaxmatov Akobir Ravshan o'g'li. (2022). LIVER ANATOMY, HISTOLOGY AND PHYSIOLOGY. INTELLECTUAL EDUCATION TECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS AND INNOVATIVE DIGITAL TOOLS, 1(11), 8-11.
6. Asfandiyorov Javodbek Mirzaali o'g'li, Mardonov Mirzabek Begzod o'g'li, Rashidov Abdulaziz Ashurali o'g'li. (2022). OXIRGI MIYA, UNING YOSHGA QARAB O'ZGARISHI. PLASHNING RELEFI. OXIRGI MIYANING OQ MODDASI. BAZAL O'ZAKLAR. PEDAGOG. 1(3), 319-326.
7. Asfandiyorov Javodbek Mirzaali o'g'li, Xushmurodov Doniyor Turg'un o'g'li, Nazarov Asadjon Fozil o'g'li. (2022). Liver Structure and Functions, Hepatocytes Information About. American Journal of Economics and Business Management. 5(11), 215-216.
8. Javodbek Asfandiyorov, Kamola Nomozova, Lochinbek Azimov, Abdullo Ibrohimov, Mahliyo Hamdamova. (2022). O 'ZBEKISTONDA SURUNKALI KASALLIKLAR. Академические исследования в современной науке. 1(17), 118-121.

9. Ahmedova Saodat Toshboltayevna, Asfandiyorov Javodbek Mirzaali o'g'li, Fozilov Nurillo Bahromjon o'g'li. (2022). SIFILIS (ZAXM) KASALLIGI, UNING ALOMATLARI VA BIRLAMCHI OQIBATLARI. PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES AND TEACHING METHODS. 2(17), 153-155.

10. Mirzaali o'g'li, A. J., Shodiqul o'g'li, X. I., Fozil o'g'li, N. A., & Davronbek Ulug'bek o'g, T. (2022). TERMINAL CASES LUNG AND HEART RESUSCITATION TRANSFER PRINCIPLES. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 10(10), 729-731.

11. Abdukamol qizi, NZ, Raxmat qizi, SX, Alisher o'g'li, AA, Raxmon o'g'li, AM, & Mirzaali o'g'li, AJ (2022). Kardiojarrohlik haqida. Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science , 3 (5), 694-696. <https://cajmns.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJMNS/article/view/1157>

12. Mirzaali o'g'li, A. J., Shodiqul o'g'li, X. I., Fozil o'g'li, N. A., Eminjon o'g'li, S. X., & Aliqul o'g'li, N. B. (2022). ANESTHESIA AND ITS GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS. Gospodarka i Innowacje., 28, 191-192.

13. Mirzaali o'g'li, A. J., Shodiqul o'g'li, X. I., Eminjon o'g'li, S. X., Aliqul o'g'li, N. B., & Begzod o'g'li, M. M. (2022). Importance of medical prevention in medicine. Texas Journal of Medical Science, 13, 175-176.

14. Asfandiyorov, J., Toshpulatov, A., Dobilov, F., Fozilov, N., & Sunnatullayeva, M. (2022). ADENOKARSINOMA KASALLIGINING UMUMIY XUSUSIYATLARI XUSUSIDA. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 1(4), 70-72.